

CONSTITUTIONAL BASIS OF REFORMS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the cases of the constitutional development of education. In addition, the international cooperation of the Tashkent State Law University and the actual implementation of the constitutional right to education are highlighted.

On April 30, 2023, the Uzbek people voted in a referendum for a new version of the Constitution for their future.

Since the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and up to this period, it began to manifest itself in all spheres of our life. Because this Constitution was created as a fruit of our independence and is performed as the anthem of our independence. Today, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has become a real social value for all of us. This is the main criterion of our socio-political life, it is an integral part of social relations, and it enters the field as a stabilizing force in our life. We will not be mistaken if we say that this Constitution arose as a force that unites society, develops its life and inspires it.

When being acquainted with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is permissible to remember about its various aspects. In particular, he defined the main principles of foreign and domestic policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The constitution is essentially a legal document. Because it was, the main law of the state, the entire state system, public life were regulated legally and legally.

From this point of view, its significance for our society is incomparable. In particular, Articles 15-16 of our Constitution state that our current social and political life, the principle of the primacy of the Constitution and the laws adopted on its basis are built based on its direct application. From this point of view, it can be recognized as a document stabilizing the legal foundations of society. Instead, it is necessary to recognize that our Constitution has an important spiritual potential. Because when creating the Constitution, we managed to legally consolidate it, taking into account its spirituality and values, dating back to the historical roots of the Uzbek people.

That is why every line written in the Constitution has become a phrase in the language of our people, a rule that has penetrated into the hearts of our people. When we read it, we can become witnesses to the fact that in each section, chapter, and line it breathes the freedom and pride of our people, which has been preserved for years. In reading this

Constitution, every reader is reading the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the universally recognized principles of international law.

This Constitution is a new document based on its fundamental essence, philosophy, and idea, in which the idea was put forward that a person is the greatest among the total possessions, and on this basis, a reasonable legal solution to the relationship between the individual and the state was found.

In order to create a democratic, legal, social and secular state, Uzbekistan is gradually implementing consistent reforms.

Noting above the role of the fundamental law in the regulation of all spheres, it is necessary to focus on the field of education, which is the main factor in the development of the state.

Article 51 of the Basic Law establishes that everyone has the right to education and provides for the development of various forms of state education, state and non-state educational organizations.

Based on this norm, we can say that the number of higher education organizations in our country is 210, including 36 universities, 48 institutes, 4 academies, 1 conservatory, 65 non-governmental organizations of higher education, 26 regional branches. Branches of foreign universities reached 30. The previous version of the Constitution did not define the role and status of non-state educational organizations. The need for higher education is realized by determining their special legal status and providing them with a number of tax and other benefits in the new version of the basic law.

Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5847 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", a number of measures are being taken to develop the higher education system.

For example, at the Tashkent State Law University under the Ministry of Justice, 7,052 students study full-time, part-time, distance learning, 4,495 students study at legal technical schools of the system, and 467 people study at academic lyceums.

The majority of students studying at the Tashkent State University of Law are given the opportunity to receive state higher education at the expense of the state, i.e. based on grants, as well as because of title documents, using the benefits provided to various categories and directions, as specified in article 51 of our Constitution.

In addition, the university fully enjoys the right to academic freedom, self-government, freedom of research and teaching in accordance with the basic law. Significant progress has been made in determining the form of education, taking into account the specifics of areas of training and specialties, introducing correspondence, distance and evening forms of education at the master's level, determining the parameters for admission to training based on a payment agreement.

In total, in the field of academic independence, the university signed 78 memorandums of understanding with partner foreign educational organizations, of which 67 foreign higher educational and research institutions and 11 international and foreign organizations implement educational student exchange programs on the basis of existing contracts, agreements and memorandums.

Tashkent State University of Law, as one of the institutions of higher education that has gained financial independence, limits the flow of funds from the budget and ensures its financial stability in exchange for paying for contracts and other services.

It would not be wrong to say that the fact that the university earned \$13,902,654 in 2022 from the payment contract form is a practical and vital expression of Article 51 of the Constitution, which serves as a guarantee of the free use of its funds.

In conclusion, we think that the new version of the basic law will serve as the legal basis for reforms in the field of education and meet the expectations of our people in this area.

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